

Eco-friendly Washing of Denim Garments Using Enzymatic Treatments

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17617079

KEYWORDS

Denim Washing
Sustainable
Washing
Water free
treatment

ABSTRACT

Sustainable washing techniques are being used more and more in the production of denim garments and fabrics. This study explores the use of water-free enzyme and ozone techniques as well as enzymatic treatments to wash denim clothing in a sustainable manner. Strength tests and colorfastness tests for washing, rubbing, and perspiration were among the evaluation criteria. The findings showed that, in comparison to conventional exhaust procedures, the enzymatic processes offered better colorfastness. Furthermore, visual assessments of every wash sample showed positive results using a range of washing methods. The environmental impact of enzymatic treatments was examined, with particular attention paid to important metrics such effluent quality, energy consumption, chemical footprint, and water utilization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Both the fashion industry and the market for everyday clothing have a high need for denim items [1]. People of all ages, but particularly young people, are very interested in denim [2]. Various value-adding techniques, such as industrial washing, give denim not only a stunning appearance but also certain practical qualities that enhance clothing. Denim garments that are washed are more popular and value-added garments to consumers [3]. These garments items are washed using various methods to alter their look, perspective, and style. Several methods are applied for washing effect on the garments such as pigment wash,

caustic wash, stone wash, acid wash, bleach was etc. [4]. These techniques change the overall look of the garments and turn attractive for customers. Additionally, starch may present in the garments which is removed by the washing [5]. Furthermore, after being purchased straight from the store or shop, washed garments might be worn. Since certain clothing shrinks after washing, washed garments can be bought in the appropriate size without taking additional shrinkage into account. Enzyme is selected among several garment washing methods to polish the fabric's surface and gradually remove color from all over the garment. [6]. In stone enzyme washing, denim garments is washed in

an industrial washing machine with pumice stones. [7].

Every year, 2 billion jeans are produced worldwide [8]. For one pair of denim trouser, bleach wash, consumes about 240 liters of water. Neutralization and spray come next, consuming around 180 liters. In case of stone wash, approximate 150 liters water is used. For rinse and softening operations utilize about 100 liters and 60 liters of water, respectively [9]. This indicates usage of very high-water consumption. Water free enzyme can be sustainable alternative for denim washing by using the pumice stones & water reducing purpose, water free enzyme with ozone process (enzymatic process) in the washing machine and produce better distressed look [10]. In denim enzyme stone process, stone replacement powder is indeed used in combination with water free enzymes. It's also called as Enzyme activator [11]. The water free enzymes are typically a blend of Cellulase and other enzymes that help break down the indigo dye on the denim fabric [12]. The water free enzymes help to further break down the indigo dye and enhance the fading effect [13]. Combining enzyme with stone can speed up the desired outcome with the least amount of damage because only stone damages garments and equipment [14]. Using water-free enzyme throughout the washing process helps to achieve the correct shade in a comparatively short period of time while maintaining the wear and tear of the garment within a bearable range.

The word "ozone" (O₃) laundry refers to a textile care concept that alternates many of the chemicals typically used in a conventional washing process with a novel use of electricity and oxygen [15]. Ozone is produced using energy and oxygen. Instead of using chemicals, ozone is applied to the wash wheel after being dissolved in water. There are numerous advantages to this fundamental shift that contribute to a wash's increased productivity and lower operating expenses.

The environmental effect of conventional washing operations is significantly reduced by Water Energy Ozone washing Systems. This technique can be used to bleach the garments. In a washing machine, ozone is dissolved in water

to bleach denim garments. Additionally, ozone gas can be used in a controlled chamber to bleach or fade denim garments [16].

In order to address the excessive water footprint of the denim washing sector, the study presents a unique sustainable denim washing technology that uses a low water ratio bio-washing procedure.

Mahmud et al. worked on a unique sustainable denim washing technology that uses a low water ratio bio-washing procedure. Bio-magic consumes a lot less water than bio-polish while yet producing similar fabric shades. However, because of the combined enzymatic and mechanical action during the procedure, the bio-magic treatment resulted in a disproportionate reduction in fabric weight as well as a noticeable fall in tear and tensile strength [17].

Another study by Hasan et al. studied the effects of several washing techniques such as enzyme wash, enzyme stone wash, heavy enzyme stone wash with bleaching on the properties of stretch denim fabric. Superior dimensional stability, tensile strength, and tear resistance were displayed by enzyme-washed textiles, although their color fastness performance was just mediocre. Excellent color fastness to rubbing was demonstrated by a heavy enzyme stone wash. Color change and staining grades for color fastness to washing, sweat, and light did not significantly differ between washing techniques. When compared to alternative techniques, enzyme washing produced superior dry and wet rubbing fastness [18].

Another study evaluated the sustainability of innovative methods like ozone washing and ozone washing with laser fading compared to conventional techniques, which concluded that ozone washing and ozone washing with laser fading are effective, environmentally friendly alternatives for sustainable denim washing practices [19].

However, several sustainable washing techniques have been individually investigated, limited research has focused on combined application of water free enzyme & ozone- based treatments on denim garments washing with

physical and mechanical impacts on fabric. In this study, performance of denim garments after water free enzyme & ozone processes are investigated and the impact on the physical and mechanical properties to assess the wearers comfort and the longevity of the final product. Furthermore, optimal proportions and application conditions for use of enzyme & ozone treatment were also determined to achieve desired washing effects. The findings offer a more eco-friendly alternative to traditional water-intensive washing methods.

2. MATERIALS & METHOD

2.1 Raw Materials

2.1.1. Fabric Used as Sample

Table 1: Sample Information

Fabric Type	Composition	Fabric Code	After Wash Color
Denim fabric used (Leg Tube)	83% Cotton 16% Polyester 1% Elastic (Direct dyed)	8093L2-V05	Blue
Denim garment used (Short Pant)	83% Cotton 16% Polyester 1% Elastic (Direct dyed)	8093L2-V05	Blue

2.1.2 Chemicals Used

ASUCEL WFC (Company: ASUCEL, Spain) was procured in solid form. Soda Ash and anti-back staining agent were purchased from chemical store, Hatkhola Bazar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

2.2 Recipe of enzymatic wash

Table 2: Washing Recipe

Enzyme (ASUCEL WFC)	
Amount	20 gm
Time	20 minutes
Temperature	25°C
Rinse	2 times

Table 3: Cleaning Recipe

Soda Ash		1 g/L
	Water	100 Liter.
	Temperature	50°C
	Time	5 minutes
	pH	5.5
		2 g/L
	Water	200 Liter.

Anti-Back stain Agent	pH	5.5
	Rinse	2 times

2.3 Preparation of Solution and Washing Procedure

Sample was loaded into an ozone machine for 100% ozone treatment/bleaching at room temperature for five minutes, and then gas cleaning for four minutes to get rid of any remaining ozone. It was then unloaded and rinsed in a washing machine with a 1:3 water-to-liquor ratio. A 1:1 (enzyme: sample) liquor ratio was used for the enzyme treatment utilizing "ASUCEL WFC" at room temperature for 20 minutes followed by a 1:5 (material: water) ratio rinse wash. Anti-back stain and soda ash (1 g/L) in a 1:5 (material: water) liquor ratio was used to clean the garments, and then they were rinsed again. Following five minutes of hydro extraction, the sample was tumble dried for forty minutes at 65°C, cooled for ten minutes, and then sent to quality control before being delivered to the finishing area.

2.4 Conventional Treatment Recipe

Table 4: Conventional Treatment Recipe

Desize	Soda Ash	1 g/L
	Water	100 Liter
	Temperature	45°C
	Time	10 minutes
	Rinse	2 times
	Enzyme	Valumax A 838
Anti-Back stain Agent		1 g/L
Water		100 Liter
Stone		25 kg
Temperature		45°C
Time		30 minutes
Rinse		2 times
Bleaching		Calcium Hypochlorite
	Water	100 Liter

	Temperature	50°C
	Time	10 minutes
	Rinse	2 times
Neutral		
	Sodium Metabisulfite	2 g/L
	Water	100 Liter
	Rinse	2 times

2.5 Conventional Washing Procedure

A batch of denim short pants weighing one kilogram requires a number of stages in the traditional washing process. Clothes are loaded, treated with water, soda ash, and anti-back stain at 50°C for 10 minutes, and then rinsed in desizing. Water, soda ash, pumice stones, and anti-back stain are all applied during the stoning process. After 30 minutes of enzyme addition at 45°C, the tone enzyme process involves rinsing and stone removal. Sodium hypochlorite is used in the bleaching process for ten minutes at 50°C, after which it is rinsed. Sodium meta-bisulphite is added and allowed to sit at room temperature for five minutes in neutralization. The next step is cleaning, which involves rinsing after 5 minutes at 50°C with soda ash and anti-back stain. After the surplus water is removed from the garments using a hydro extractor, they are placed in a drying machine set to 65°C for 40 minutes.

2.6 Characterization

2.6.1 Color Fastness to Water Test

Color fastness to washing is the first and most important requirement of buyers in the case of a fastness test. Standard test method was followed as ISO 105 C06: test for color fastness to washing. Color fastness to washing is defined as a textile specimen that comes into contact with one or two specified adjacent fabrics, is mechanically agitated under specified conditions of time and temperature in a soap solution, then rinsed and dried. The change in color of the specimen and the staining of the adjacent fabric are then evaluated using grey scales. Here Sample Fabric and multi fiber fabric is 10 cm x 4cm.

2.6.2 Color Fastness to Washing Test

Color fastness to water determines how much the fabric resists its color from fading or

bleeding when expose to water followed by the EN ISO 105-E01:2013 standard test method.

After that, the specimen was cleaned and allowed to dry. The specimen's color shift and the staining of the surrounding material were assessed using greyscales. This sample weighed 1 gram, and the multifiber fabric measured 100 x 40 mm.

2.6.3 Color Fastness to Perspiration Test

The EN ISO 105-E04:2013 standard test technique is used to determine a fabric's color fastness to water, which measures how resistant it is to fading or bleeding when exposed to perspiration. The quantities of sodium chloride, sodium dihydrogenorthophosphate, and L-histidine mono-hydrochloride monohydrate in this freshly prepared solution are 0.5 gm/l, 5 gm/l, and 2.2 gm/l, respectively, according to the acid solution formula. Its pH is 5.5 after being corrected with 0.1N sodium hydroxide. For the alkali solution, the concentrations of sodium chloride, disodium dihydrogenorthophosphate, and L-histidine mono-hydrochloride monohydrate are 0.5 gm/l, 5 gm/l, and 2.5 gm/l, respectively, in this freshly prepared solution. Its pH is 8.0 after being corrected with 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

2.6.4 Color Fastness to Rubbing Test

Rubbing fastness, which is measured in both dry and wet situations, is the resistance of color transfer from a fabric's surface to another material when rubbing. The test uses two procedures, ISO 105-X12 and AATCC-08, to detect the staining level on a designated test cloth. The wet pickup of the rubbing cloth is 100% in ISO 105-X12 and 65% in AATCC-08. The test cloth is wetted in accordance with the procedure's specifications during wet rubbing, and staining is assessed using a gray scale for comparison, guaranteeing a consistent evaluation of color transfer resistance. 5 cm square was sample size.

2.6.5 pH Test

The samples' pH levels were ascertained immediately using a digital pH meter (Ecoscen, Eutech Instruments, Singapore).

2.6.6 Tensile Strength Test

A universal tensile testing machine (Testometric, M250-3CT, India) with an accurate

load cell capacity of 300N was utilized to measure the mechanical strength and evaluate the samples' tensile characteristics.

2.6.7 Tear Strength Test

A machine with a consistent rate of extension was used to measure the fabric's strength according to Ballistic Pendulum Method (Elmendorf). Samples of fabric measuring 20 cm by 5 cm were made.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Visual Appearance of the Samples of Conventional and Enzymatic Treatment

Fig. 1: Washed fabric sample (a) conventional and (b) enzymatic treatment

From the visual observation, it was found that, utilizing less amount of chemical and water, enzymatic treatment performed better than conventional treated samples.

3.2 Color Fastness to Washing

Color fastness to wash determines how much the fabric resists its color from fading due to washing. From the test, it was observed that both conventional washing method and enzymatic method exhibited same performance with respect to the wash fastness property. This may due to the both conventional and enzymatic method maintain integrity of the dye-fiber bonding. Enzymatic chemicals properly created bond between dye and fibers on the fabric, that successfully resist dye from washing out. This indicates the performed enzymatic method not only ecofriendly but also gives similar result to conventional method. From the Figure 2, both conventional and enzymatic process demonstrated washing fastness 4-5 in color staining grey scale which is sufficient for end use application.

Fig. 2: Colour fastness to wash of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples.

3.3 Color Fastness to Water Test Result

Color fastness to water determines how much the fabric resists its color from fading or bleeding when expose to water. After test, both the samples should similarly result although enzymatic treatment was performed with less chemical and water. Both conventional and enzymatic sample showed fastness to water 4-5 in color staining grey scale that is showed in the Figure 3. This may due to this could be because the dye-fiber bonding is maintained using both traditional and sustainable methods. Water-free chemicals efficiently prevent dye from washing off by appropriately creating a link between the fabric's fibers and the dye. By this result, it can be concluded that stone washed sample with less water can perform as like as chemical washing process.

Fig. 3: Colour fastness to water of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples

3.4 Color Fastness to Perspiration Test Result

Color fastness to water determines the fabric's resistance its color from fading or

bleeding when expose to acidic perspiration. After observation, fastness value was found 4-5 for conventional and enzymatic sample in color staining grey scale. From the Figure 4, it is shown that for all types of fabric in multifiber fabric (DW), exhibited similar performance with respect to perspiration. This may due to the This might be because, when exposed to acidic sweat, the dye molecules were successfully fixed inside the fabric structure by both the traditional and water-free procedures, avoiding noticeable dye migration or color bleeding. By this result, it can be concluded that stone washed sample can resist perspiration similar to conventional treatment and suitable for end use.

Fig. 4: Colour fastness to perspiration of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples.

3.6 Color Fastness to Rubbing Test

Result

Color fastness to water determines the fabric's resistance its color from fading or bleeding when subjected to friction and ensured the durability during use. From the Figure 5, sample of conventional and enzymatic showed fastness value 4 in case of dry rubbing. In wet rubbing, enzymatic sample showed higher fastness property than conventional sample. From this result, it is concluded that, following the sustainable washing method, material can exhibit more fastness to rubbing than conventional method.

Fig. 5: Color fastness to rubbing of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples

3.7 pH Test Analysis

pH test determines the acidity or alkalinity of the washed fabrics. This test is necessary to evaluate whether that material is safe or not for skin contact. Figure 6 showed little difference in pH in between two samples. enzymatic sample exhibited pH value 5.1 whereas conventional sample 6.2. Because very little amount of water just utilized as a washing medium in the water-free approach, mildly acidic residues from the alternative treatment agents or procedures may remain. However, the traditional approach, which usually entails a thorough water rinse, may be more successful in neutralizing acidic substances, leading to a pH that is closer to neutral.

Fig. 6: pH value of wash of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples.

3.8 Tensile Test Report

Tensile test is performed to evaluate a material's mechanical properties, such as strength, elasticity that will conform whether the material will be suitable for required end use or not. This test was performed following the Grab

Method. In the Figure 7, enzymatic sample showed higher tensile strength in case of both warp and weft way samples. Fiber weakening or swelling, which can happen with conventional washing treatments, may have been minimized by not using water throughout the treatment process. Additionally, by better maintaining or even strengthening the fabric's mechanical structure, the alternative treatment chemicals or procedures employed in the enzymatic treatment may have had a reinforcing effect. This indicates that, sustainable treatment not only improved the sustainability but also increase mechanical performance in terms of tensile strength.

Fig. 7: Tensile strength performance of conventional and sustainable method's sample.

3.8 Tear Strength Test Report

Tear strength assessment is done for determining the resistance of materials against tearing. From the observation in Figure 8, it was found that in case of warp way samples, almost similar strength found whereas, in case of weft way sample, strength was higher in sustainable sample than conventional sample. This may happen due to the similar reason with tensile strength that fibers are not swelling or weakening by high amount of water as conventional treatment.

Fig. 8: Tear strength of conventional and enzymatic treatment samples.

4. CONCLUSION

According to a study on enzymatic treatment for sustainable denim washing, the enzymatic process successfully replaces traditional washing, providing comparable or better fabric performance while using less resource. Both methods gave equal findings for color fastness against washing, water, and perspiration, with fastness values of 4-5, suggesting robust dye-fiber bonding. Due to less fiber weakening, the water-free sample had a greater tensile strength than the conventional one, and the water-free approach also performed better in wet rubbing fastness. The water-free sample performed better in the weft direction, but its pH was slightly more acidic and its tear strength was comparable in the warp direction. These results demonstrate that the environmentally friendly and resource-efficient sustainable water-free method can produce results that are comparable to or better than traditional denim washing techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to express our profound appreciation to Creative Wash Ltd - 04. in Bangladesh for kindly giving the lab space we needed to carry out our research.

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